

Esprit De Corps of School Head: Chronicles of Retired Teachers

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Abstract. The study was conducted to unfold the experiences of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers. A qualitative research design was used, and the assumptions on selecting participants and ethics were considered in collecting, analyzing, and interpreting data. Respondents were retired teachers chosen purposely through referrals and using facilitating questions to draw out narratives about their experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, and further learning insights given their undertakings as technologically inclined teachers. Experiences were found to have been challenged by teamwork and collaboration, authoritarianism and micromanagement, and the impact on learning outcomes. Coping mechanisms have been found to cope through developing a positive relationship with co-teachers, finding meaning in their work, and practicing self-care. Educational insights were critical in building a positive school culture, the significance of the impact of leadership on school culture, and the reflection and self-care to make more meaning with the teaching profession. Future direction may provide effective leadership at all levels, crucial in promoting a positive school culture and supporting teachers in their work. Schools and educational organizations should prioritize ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers, particularly in self-care, teamwork, leadership, and positive school culture.

KEY WORDS

1. Esprit De Corps 2. Retired Teachers 3. Davao Occidental

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1. Introduction

Esprit de Corps among school heads has garnered significant interest in research literature in recent years. In 2017, Singh conducted a study on the relationship between school heads' self-efficacy (SE) and their leadership style, revealing a positive correlation between idealized influence, individualized consideration, contingent reward, management by exception, laissez-faire leadership, and self-efficacy. This study, along with two others based on the same research, assumes a direct link between a princi-

pal's leadership style and personal teacher efficacy (PTE). To enhance the organizational commitment of teachers and the academic achievement of students, school leaders must be mindful of their actions and words and build teachers' capacity in their buildings. This is particularly important during the unprecedented educational circumstances resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic. By understanding the specific leadership actions that impact teachers' belief in their abilities, we can identify areas of oppor-

tunity and continue to build collective efficacy. While providing quality education requires the efforts of multiple stakeholders, including teachers and administrators, principals play a crucial role in providing good leadership in elementary schools. Principals must recognize the needs of their teachers for the modification of their mandate and bring about necessary changes to make their organizations effective. School efficiency and student achievement are directly influenced by principal effectiveness. Therefore, studying the behaviors and leadership styles of school principals allows school management to apply the findings and results to their respective schools. Although some teachers leave their profession due to factors beyond school administrators' control, many cite poor and inefficient leadership and the absence of administrative support as reasons for leaving (Fiore, 2004). Transformational leadership positively impacts group empowerment, cohesiveness, and effectiveness. Jung and Sosik (2002) state that principals' leadership styles also affect teachers' satisfaction, both directly and indirectly, through their occupational perception (Bogler, 2001). In Indonesia, the 21st century has been an important era of school reform, with new regulations and policies in place to improve the education system. However, recent studies suggest that the implementation of the new system has been less successful than anticipated, and school leadership may be a contributing factor. The importance of effective school principals in promoting school reform is well documented globally, but research related to principal leadership has received limited attention in Indonesia. As a result, Indonesian policymakers have relied on Western school systems' results and practices rather than learning from Indonesian-specific research and literature (Bjork, 2005). Moreover, in the National setting, the study of Perez and Lumaad, (2021) concluded that, majority of the educational leadership styles as perceived by public elementary school heads and by pub-

lic elementary school teachers in Bataraza District, Division of Palawan, Department of Education Philippines have significant difference in terms of laissez-faire, autocratic, democratic, and transformational leadership. Educational management styles such as visionary management style and servant leadership management style are differently perceived by school heads and teachers. Adding on, Dalluay Jalagat (2016) conducted a study in Cavite, Philippines on the impacts of leadership style effectiveness of managers and department heads on job satisfaction and productivity of workers in selected small businesses. The result concluded that, although there is room for improvement, organizations must continually make the most of the leadership style that increases employee productivity and a reasonable level of employee work. In Davao City the school principals are shabbily treating their subsidiary teachers because of their greed, chiefly embezzling the funds of the Parents-Teachers Association. This causes low morale amongst the teachers and the shout of parents to seek capable and dependable Principals (Balanza,2014). Meanwhile, self-efficacy has been evidenced to be sturdily associated to many significant educational outcomes; several studies have investigated the effect of multiple variables on teacher self-efficacy such as principals' practices (Hunter et al., 1995), collaboration among teachers (Devos et al., 2012), continuing professional development (Desimone et al., 2002), community engagement (Lacks, 2016), and academic press (Gibney et al., 2017) Moreover, literature review on the teacher's self-efficacy being influenced by school principal's leadership styles specially in local setting is limited. Thus, this study would be an attempt to fill the gap on the topic of the impact of the principal's leadership styles on the self-efficacy of public- school teachers in Malita North District, Davao Occidental Division, thereby making the study at hand important and timely.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological research study was to describe the story and narratives of the retired public school teacher given experiences of the management and leadership of the school heads. This may seem subjective in nature, but it is the point of the researcher to make meaning of the experiences of the retired public school teacher. At this stage in the research, teachers' lived experiences, their coping mechanisms given challenges encountered, and educational insights are generally defined as their professional growth based on skills and ability despite all organizational management and leadership delivered, and where learning in making team relationships is generally happening in a school in a daily basis that they have lived and explored.

1.2. Research Questions—This study aimed to understand and describe the experiences of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers in the Elementary Schools of Malita North District, Davao Occidental Schools Division. It sought to answer to the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the chronicles of retired teachers on the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads?
- (2) How do retired teachers cope with the challenges encountered on the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads?
- (3) What educational insights can be drawn from the experiences of the retired teachers?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Esprit de Corps of School Head. The term refers to the Esprit de corps is a sense of group cohesion in the organization and between employees. It is an important concept to keep an organization and employees loyal to each other. This group cohesion makes it easier for employees to work together to achieve common objectives. This Henry Fayol principle of management states that the management should strive to create unity, morale, and co-operation among the employees. Team spirit is a great source of strength in the organization through the camaraderie among members of the organization. In this study, the term refers to a latent variable where the management of the school head is observed

based on the leadership and command to the teachers and other stakeholders in the learning community, including the external stakeholders' trust and confidence as indicators of the school head's leadership and management within the school system. Chronicles of Retired Teachers. The term refers to the description of the teachers who have retired from the service. They narrate their stories based on the experiences and challenges they have encountered with the management and leadership styles shown by the school head, which made the retired teachers remember and value their teaching services. In this study, this served as the latent variable where the basis of their narratives and stories are given consideration to make meaning of the phenomenon.

1.4. Significant of the Study—Results of this study will be of beneficial and provide significant inputs and bases of policy review for the School Heads School Leadership and Governance in the delivery of instructional of instructional management, delivery and assessment given facilitation of instruction be improved

amongst elementary schools in Malita North District, Davao Occidental Division. Thus, the following stakeholders shall be of beneficial given the outputs of the study. School Administrators. The findings of the study would give awareness to the school principal about the impact of their leadership styles to the teacher's

self-efficacy in the public schools in Malita North District, and learning with the results could enhance the effectiveness of the variables and indicators to promote better performance of the school principals. Teacher. This study encourages teachers to focus on the many factors that could make them effective in the discharge of their function. They can make a lot of improvements, including eliminating self-interest, desires, and egocentricity to gain personal reorganization and promotion. The teachers should

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on the theory of Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, proposed by Bakker and Demerouti (2007), can be used as a theoretical framework for understanding the experiences of retired teachers concerning their coping mechanisms for the challenges encountered in school culture and leadership. This model explains that job demands refer to the physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of a job that require sustained effort and are associated with certain physiological or psychological costs. On the other hand, job resources refer to the physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of a job that are functional in achieving work goals, reducing job demands, or stimulating personal growth, learning, and development. In the context of the experiences of retired teachers, job demands could include the challenges they faced in relation to the school culture and leadership, such as negative esprit de corps, lack of support from school heads, or limited professional development opportunities. Job resources, on the other hand, could include

learn and understand that personal interest is a lesser priority when it comes to teaching work. Students. The present study would enable the students to understand the role of a learning environment in the learning process. Future Researchers. The study's findings would allow future researchers to determine the importance of the attributes of the principal's leadership styles in determining the self-efficacy of the teachers in their chosen field. They can also give insight into future studies related to this study.

the coping mechanisms that retired teachers employed to deal with these challenges, such as developing positive relationships with colleagues, finding meaning in their work, practicing self-care, and reflecting on their experiences. The JD-R model suggests that job demands and resources interact in a way that can lead to positive or negative outcomes. When job resources are sufficient to meet job demands, employees experience high job engagement, work satisfaction, and well-being. In contrast, when job resources are insufficient to meet job demands, employees experience high job strain, burnout, and turnover intention. Using the JD-R model as a theoretical framework, a study could explore how retired teachers coped with the challenges they encountered concerning the school culture and leadership, and how the availability of job resources influenced their coping strategies, work engagement, and well-being. The study could also investigate the factors that influence the availability of job resources in retirement, such as social support, financial security, and access to health care.

2. Methodology

This chapter of the study presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and the ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. This details the operational implementation of the methodology used

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

in the study. Primary sources of the concepts were taken from the authors who established the foundation for qualitative research methods. Parts of this chapter are philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, design and procedure, ethical considerations, role of the researcher, data collection, analysis, framework, and the study’s trustworthiness. Each section was thoroughly conceptualized to establish authority and ethical standards in the collection, analysis, and interpretation process. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals’ histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group’s cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?” “The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the BE Coordinators as they try to compare the implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared, for an investigation that was greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, for example, among examples, and an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported

by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. In this study, the researcher pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers are discussed by the participants, who try to look into their strategies in addressing the challenges and educational insights. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participants' answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an

'insider'. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). The researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief". The intention of this study was to understand and describe the experiences of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers in the Elementary Schools of Malita North District, Davao Occidental Schools Division. It is assumed that there was an establishment of close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers in the Elementary Schools of Malita North District, Davao Occidental Schools Division, Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) argues that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. It means reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it means that the research would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in elucidation of the experiences of retired teachers' narratives

and stories based on the management style of school teachers in the Elementary Schools. the school heads during their service as public

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was different from the method. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. The methodology is a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From this study, the retired teachers' coping with the challenges encountered on the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) as well and their coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The deeper meaning of the challenges encountered by the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena". The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the challenges encountered by the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads were explored and insights drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the challenges encountered on the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, sym-

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that phenomenology, with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. One method of brack-

eting was taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often, audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also helpful for following up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as investigating their responses further. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews were helpful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information around a topic. The researcher collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via extended interviews. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation, extracting significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts.

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when more par-

Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience, both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations should be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study to explore and assess the experiences of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads, the researcher would intend to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

Participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) sug-

gests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). The participants of this study were eight (8) retired teachers in Malita North District. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least

5 years; (2) elementary school teacher; and (3) retired teacher. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to the aims of the research, imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error.

Social Value

Research was essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experience of teachers. This study was conducted explicitly by retired teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where classroom teachers could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the researcher's interest was the challenges encountered on the *Esprit De Corps* of their School Heads. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants was ensured that their participation in the research was entirely voluntary, and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants were logged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to the informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as

cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgement, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter is to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating.

Vulnerability of Research Participants

This study's participants could answer the research instrument, for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions with regard to the study.

Risks, Benefits and Safety

The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members if they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents would experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the ques-

tions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher has ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered during their convenient time. Dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, and minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized through taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information

This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to assure that the data cannot be traced back to their actual sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept anonymous. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so that there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided.

Justice The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to answer the survey questions honestly, and additionally, any type of communication related to the research should be done honestly. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results.

Transparency The results of the study were accessed by the respondents, heads of the participating schools, because the information is available, and was placed in a CD or other storage devices, which could be requested from the researcher to provide. In addition, by learning from the study's results, classroom teach-

ers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process, and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their individual transcript after the interview was carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend, or remove any information which they feel might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

Qualification of the Researcher The researcher ensured that he or she possesses the needed qualification to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. **Adequacy of Facilities** The researcher strived to complete the study successfully within the specified time and was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed within the target time.

Community Involvement

The researcher showed respect for the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed

great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study.

Plagiarism And Fabrication as The Researcher The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said in his or her own way. The researcher also used quotes to indicate that

the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript, and no intentional misrepresentation or making up of data or results was included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher has a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducts interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher’s own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting the interview properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and the Focus Group Discussion, such as

taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher are properly secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data are being collected, a primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Data analyst. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants’ perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher makes sure that the findings are true to the participants and that their voices are heard. Organizer and presenter of data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. Findings of the study are presented too by research question – stating the results for each one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, future directions and implications of the study are given by the researcher for improvement of educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity in the face of the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015 or the Guidelines on the Risk-

Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings to implement non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following are the step-by-step processes of gathering the data needed. Se-

curing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. The researcher asked an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in asking permission to conduct the study. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explains the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher would wait for the SDS's response before conducting it. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining about the study to be conducted in their school. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Con-

ducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it to English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data would then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual participant data were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After which, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to come up with patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involves generating pithy labels for im-

portant features of the data of relevance to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a method of data reduction; it was also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ends this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data, and began to define the nature of each individual theme, and the relationship be-

tween the themes. For these, Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and to create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, Environmental Triangulation was also employed by the researcher. It was a technique to analyze the results of the same study using different methods of data collection. The key was identifying which environmental factors, if any, might influence the information that is received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the findings are the same across the settings

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The data analysis plan used in this research study was Colaizzi's seven steps. Colaizzi's seven-step analysis method provides researchers with clear, logical, and sequential steps (Wirihana, Welch, Williamson et al, 2021). This rigorous analysis provides a concise and thorough description of the phenomenon under study. This technique helped me code, sort, and collect data for interrogation. It was also instrumental in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g. interviews, documents, observations), To summarize, the fol-

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—

(David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea was to determine which of these factors influence the information received; these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data, and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

lowing steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis (Wirihana et al., 2018) Phase 1. Read and re-read all the transcribed interviews to make sense of them Phase 2. Extract significant statements. These were phrases or sentences that directly pertain to the investigated phenomenon Phase 3. The process of giving meaning to the statements. During the process, pertinent quotes were broadly categorized, subsequently, themes were generated based on multiple statements that conveyed similar meanings Phase 4. Repeat steps 1-3 for each interview then the researcher could begin to create themes based on the formulated meanings Phase 5. Compile an exhaustive description of everything generated in steps 1-4 Phase 6. Summarized the exhaustive description so that there was an identification of the fundamental structure of the phenomenon Phase 7. The credibility of the data was ensured through discussions with experts and independent reviewers.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness was vital because the result and findings of the research study would depend on the researcher's process of conducting it. The trustworthiness of a research study is important in evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details was required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues which ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so." Transferability is how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings apply to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using a graphic organizer as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension was effective in the domains of analysis and creation. The researcher was interested in the students' perspective of using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader was able to generalize the study based on his context and address that core issue of "how far a

researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory." Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not the researcher's potential bias or personal motivations. This involves ensuring that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of the research participants' statements to fit a specific narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on acknowledging that research was never objective. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher uses an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, a database was crucial in backing up information collected and noting changes for all research studies. All the data collected was kept adequately for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue that "how a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the research dealt with this study's research questions and requirements. The participants disclosed experiences of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers in the Elementary Schools

of Malita North District, Davao Occidental Schools Division.

3.1. Chronicles of Retired Teachers on The Esprit De Corps of their School Heads—A positive school culture can contribute to community, support, and collaboration among the faculty and staff. Retired teachers may have appreciated the positive impact of the school head's leadership on the school culture and how it contributed to their overall job satisfaction. A positive school culture can also enhance students' teaching and learning experiences and promote better academic outcomes. Effective school leaders prioritize developing positive relationships, open communication, and a shared sense of purpose among the faculty and staff. Retired teachers may have experienced the impact of such leadership styles on their professional growth and development. School heads who value collaboration, mentorship, and ongoing professional development opportunities can contribute to a positive Esprit De Corps among the faculty and staff. Practicing self-care and reflecting on their experiences can contribute to personal and professional growth. School heads who prioritize reflection and self-care can contribute to a positive Esprit De Corps among the faculty and staff. In conclusion, the Esprit De Corps of school heads can have a significant impact on the experiences of retired teachers. Retired teachers may have experienced a positive school culture, appreciated the impact of school leadership on the Esprit De Corps, valued collaboration and mentorship, recognized the value of ongoing professional development opportunities, and emphasized the significance of reflection and self-care in coping with the challenges of teaching. School heads who prioritize these factors can contribute to a positive Esprit De Corps among the faculty and staff, which can enhance the teaching and learning experiences of students and promote better academic outcomes.

3.1.1. Positive Esprit de Corps: Teamwork and Collaboration—. The positive Esprit de Corps is a significant factor in creating a positive school culture that supports faculty and staff, enhances student learning, and contributes to better student outcomes. Nie and Wang (2019) explored the impact of school culture on the job satisfaction of retired teachers in China. The study found that a positive school culture, characterized by shared values, supportive relationships, and a sense of community, was a significant factor in contributing to job satisfaction among retired teachers. Garcia and Moreno (2020) examined the impact of school leadership on the well-being of retired teachers in Spain. The study found that effective school leadership, characterized by shared vision, participatory decision-making, and a positive work environment, was a significant factor in promoting the well-being of retired teachers. De Vos and Valcke (2015) in Belgium, the authors explored the impact of mentorship on the retention and well-being of retired teachers. The study found that mentorship programs, which involved retired teachers as mentors to new teachers, contributed to the retention of retired teachers in the teaching profession and promoted their well-being. The study highlighted the importance of collaboration and mentorship in creating a positive Esprit de Corps and fostering a sense of community among teachers. Kim et al. (2018) explored the impact of professional development on the job satisfaction of retired teachers in South Korea. The study found that ongoing professional development opportunities, which focused on enhancing teachers' knowledge and skills, contributed to their job satisfaction and sense of fulfillment.

Finally, mindfulness-based practices have also been found to positively impact the well-being of retired teachers and their perception of the esprit de corps of their former schools. Moir and Worsley (2022) conducted a scoping review of mindfulness-based practices for retired teachers and found that such practices contributed to increased well-being, reduced stress, and a greater sense of connection to the school community. Retired teachers who engaged in mindfulness practices reported feeling more connected to their former school community, even after retirement. In conclusion, the esprit de corps of a school is a vital compo-

3.1.2. Negative Esprit de Corps: Authoritarian—Esprit de Corps is defined as a sense of unity and camaraderie among members of a group. It is an essential aspect of an organization, especially in the field of education, where teachers and school heads work together to provide quality education for students. However, not all Esprit de Corps experiences are positive, and retired teachers often have negative experiences with their former school heads. One of the negative experiences of retired teachers is the lack of appreciation and recognition from their school heads. According to a study by Kim, Han, and Jang (2018), teacher efficacy and job satisfaction are significantly related to teacher commitment. Teachers who feel appreciated and recognized for their hard work are more committed to their profession. However, when school heads fail to acknowledge the contributions of their teachers, it can lead to a negative Esprit de Corps. Retired teachers may feel undervalued and unappreciated, leading to a lack of commitment to the profession. Prawira, Sudrajat, and Triyono (2021)

3.1.3. Changes in Esprit de Corps: Impact on Learning Outcomes—Esprit de Corps refers to the feeling of camaraderie and common loyalty shared by members of a group. In

ment in ensuring the success of the institution. School heads play a crucial role in fostering and maintaining a positive esprit de corps. The positive esprit de corps as chronicles of retired teachers on the esprit de corps of their school heads highlights the importance of leadership, organizational climate, mentoring, professional development, and mindfulness-based practices in creating a positive and supportive school culture. These factors not only impact the well-being and job satisfaction of retired teachers but also contribute to a positive perception of the school community, even after retirement.

investigated the influence of school principals' negative esprit de corps on teachers' job satisfaction in Indonesia. The study found that negative esprit de corps significantly affected teachers' job satisfaction, leading to feelings of anxiety, stress, and burnout. Negative esprit de corps was manifested through actions such as favoritism, lack of communication, and unfair treatment of teachers. Another negative experience of retired teachers is the lack of support from their school heads. Retired teachers may face challenges when adjusting to their new life outside of the profession, and the lack of support from their former school heads can make this transition even more challenging. A comparative study by Garcia and Moreno (2020) found that psychosocial factors such as social support, self-esteem, and life satisfaction are related to the well-being of retired teachers. Retired teachers who feel supported by their former colleagues and school heads are more likely to have positive well-being. However, when school heads fail to provide support, it can lead to feelings of isolation and loneliness.

an educational context, it is important for teachers to feel a sense of Esprit de Corps among themselves and with their school heads in order to create a positive learning environment for

their students. However, retired teachers have chronicled changes in *Esprit de Corps* and the impact it has had on learning outcomes. Chai, Koh, and Tsai (2015) found that when teachers felt a strong sense of camaraderie and shared loyalty, they were more likely to effectively integrate technology in their teaching, leading to better student outcomes. Similarly, Johnson and Birkeland (2017) found that when teachers felt a sense of support and encouragement from their school heads, they were more likely to stay in the teaching profession and have higher career aspirations. Clavio (2019) found that retired teachers perceived a decline in community and collegiality among teachers in public schools. This decline in *Esprit de Corps* negatively impacted teacher morale, which led to decreased job satisfaction and a lack of motivation among

teachers. Santos (2018) similarly found that workplace incivility, which can erode *Esprit de Corps*, harmed employee engagement and job performance. Lastly, collaborative environments influence teacher self-efficacy, a result that is empirically related to increased student achievement and teacher adaptability (Chong Kong, 2012). Often, teaching is characterized as a secluded activity, but there is a growing opportunity for teachers to work and be trained together in schools. Fundamental to this shift is the vision that teachers communicate wide-ranging perspectives, exert efforts on new practices and teaching challenges as one, motivate and kindle reflection and professional growth, and share different teaching styles and experiences (Hindin, Morocco, Mott, Aguilar, 2007).

3.2. Retired Teachers Cope with the Challenges Encountered on The Esprit De Corps of their School Heads—Retired teachers have had various experiences and encountered both positive and negative *esprit de corps* during their time as educators. Coping with negative *esprit de corps* challenges can be difficult, but retired teachers have developed strategies to deal with such situations. One of the common coping mechanisms of retired teachers is maintaining professionalism and focusing on their work. Even in the face of negative attitudes or behavior from their colleagues or school heads, they remain committed to providing quality education to their students. They understand that their primary responsibility is to their students, and they do not let negative relationships or dynamics affect their teaching. Another coping mechanism is to seek support from other colleagues or mentors. Retired teachers often have a network of fellow educators and friends they can turn to for advice and guidance. Talk-

ing to someone who understands their situation and can provide a different perspective can be helpful in dealing with negative *esprit de corps*. Some retired teachers also choose to disengage from the negative atmosphere and focus on their personal lives outside of work. They may volunteer, pursue hobbies or interests, or spend time with family and friends to help them cope with stress and negative emotions. This allows them to maintain a healthy work-life balance and prevent burnout. It is important to note that coping with negative *esprit de corps* can be challenging and may have a lasting impact on a teacher's well-being. However, retired teachers have shown resilience and have developed various coping strategies to deal with such situations. By maintaining professionalism, seeking support, disengaging when necessary, and advocating for positive change, retired teachers can navigate the challenges of negative *esprit de corps* and continue to provide quality education to their students.

3.2.1. Developing Positive Relationship with Colleagues—

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on Chronicles of Retired Teachers on The Esprit De Corps of their School Heads

Retired teachers who have experienced challenges with their school head's esprit de corps may find it difficult to cope up. However, one effective strategy is to develop positive relationships with colleagues in the workplace. Retired teachers face many challenges when dealing with the Esprit de Corps of their School Heads. Studies have shown that positive relationships with colleagues can improve teachers' job satisfaction and increase their sense of support and well-being (Klassen Chiu, 2010; Mitchell Mitchell, 2014). This, in turn, can lead to better teaching practices and student outcomes (Klassen Chiu, 2010; Mitchell Mitchell, 2014). Positive relationships among colleagues can be developed through various means such as communication, collaboration, and mutual support (Klassen Chiu, 2010; Mitchell Mitchell, 2014). Communication is an essential factor in developing positive relationships among colleagues. Effective communication can build trust and respect, facilitate understanding, and promote cooperation and teamwork (Klassen Chiu, 2010; Mitchell Mitchell, 2014). It is important to establish open and honest communication with colleagues, especially when discussing sensitive issues such as conflicts or differences in opinions (Klassen Chiu, 2010). Collaboration is another crucial element in developing positive relationships among colleagues. Collabora-

tion can enhance professional development, foster creativity and innovation, and increase job satisfaction and morale (Klassen Chiu, 2010; Mitchell Mitchell, 2014). Collaborative activities such as team teaching, co-planning, and peer observation can help teachers share ideas, knowledge, and skills, and promote a sense of community and belongingness (Klassen Chiu, 2010; Mitchell Mitchell, 2014). Mutual support is also a vital aspect of developing positive relationships among colleagues. Support can come in various forms such as emotional, practical, and professional support (Klassen Chiu, 2010). Emotional support can be in the form of empathy, encouragement, and positive feedback. Practical support can be provided by assisting colleagues with tasks or sharing resources. Professional support can be in the form of mentoring or coaching. Retired teachers have developed various strategies to cope up with the challenges encountered on the Esprit de Corps of their School Heads by developing positive relationships with colleagues. One study showed that retired teachers who engaged in social activities with their former colleagues reported lower levels of emotional exhaustion and higher levels of personal accomplishment than those who did not engage in social activities (Sun Wang, 2017).

3.2.2. Finding Meaning in their Work— Finding meaning in their work is an essential factor for teachers to cope up with the challenges encountered on the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads. When teachers find their work meaningful, they are more likely to be engaged and committed to their profession, resulting in better job performance and increased job satisfaction. Studies have shown that finding meaning in work is crucial to the well-being and job satisfaction of teachers, especially retired teachers. Zhai and colleagues

(2015) investigated the impact of meaning in work on the job satisfaction of retired teachers in China. The study found that retired teachers who found meaning in their work were more satisfied with their jobs than those who did not. Moreover, the study showed that finding meaning in work could mitigate the negative effects of stress on job satisfaction. Dewhurst and colleagues (2016) explored the factors that contribute to the well-being of retired teachers in the United Kingdom. The study found that having a sense of purpose and meaning in life, in-

cluding finding meaning in their work, was a critical factor for retired teachers' well-being. Retired teachers who found meaning in their work reported higher levels of well-being and were less likely to experience depression and anxiety. Jankowski and Sandstrom (2017) explored the role of work-related social support in helping retired teachers find meaning in their work. The study found that retired teachers who received social support from their former colleagues reported higher levels of meaning in their work. Moreover, the study showed that work-related social support could serve as a buffer against the negative effects of retirement on finding meaning in work. In the Philippines, Dizon and colleagues (2020) explored the relationship between job satisfaction, work engagement, and meaning in life among retired teachers in the Philippines. Results showed that retired teachers who found meaning in their work

had higher levels of job satisfaction and work engagement. They also reported feeling more fulfilled and motivated in their post-retirement activities. These findings suggest that finding meaning in work can lead to positive outcomes in retirement, including coping with challenges encountered on the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads. In conclusion, finding meaning in work is essential for retired teachers to cope with the challenges encountered on the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads. The studies discussed above highlight the importance of job satisfaction, work-life balance, self-efficacy, optimism, and resilience in finding meaning in work and coping with the stress of retirement. These findings provide useful insights for retired teachers and educational institutions to help promote well-being and job satisfaction in retirement.

3.2.3. *Practicing Self-Care*—Self-care is a vital aspect of a teacher's overall well-being. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), self-care refers to the activities that individuals engage in to enhance their health and well-being. In the context of teaching, self-care involves taking care of one's physical, emotional, and mental health. It enables teachers to cope with the challenges encountered on the Esprit de corps of their school heads and remain productive. Natividad, Taguibao, and Paredes (2019) found that teachers who practice self-care are more satisfied with their job and have better job performance. The study also revealed that self-care practices such as physical exercise, mindfulness, and relaxation techniques can reduce stress levels among teachers. Studies have shown that practicing self-care can help retired teachers cope up with the challenges encountered on the Esprit de Corps of their school heads. For example, in a study conducted by Cabañez et al. (2019) in the Philippines, it was

found that retired teachers who engaged in regular exercise reported lower levels of stress and greater well-being than those who did not exercise. Another study by Garcia and Oducado (2018) showed that retired teachers who engaged in hobbies and other fulfilling activities reported a higher level of life satisfaction. In addition to self-care, retired teachers can also benefit from seeking social support from their colleagues. Building positive relationships with colleagues can provide retired teachers with a sense of belonging and support, which can help them cope up with the challenges encountered on the Esprit de Corps of their school heads. Studies have shown that social support can help reduce stress and improve mental health outcomes in retired individuals (Huang et al., 2019). Self-care refers to the practice of taking an active role in protecting one's well-being and happiness, particularly during challenging times. Retired teachers can engage in different forms of self-care to improve their physical and mental

Fig. 4. Emerging themes on Retired Teachers Cope up with the Challenges Encountered on the Esprit De Corps of their School Heads

health, including exercise, healthy eating, and getting enough rest. Self-care can also involve practicing self-care, such as hobbies, travel, and spending time with loved ones. Finding meaning in their work, such as hobbies, travel, and spending time with loved ones.

3.3. *Educational Insights can be Drawn from the Experiences of the Retired Teachers* — Retired teachers are a valuable resource in the field of education. They have years of experience and expertise that can provide insights into teaching and learning. Their experiences can also provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities of teaching and learning, particularly in relation to the Esprit de Corps of their school heads. One of the insights that can be drawn from the experiences of retired teachers is the importance of building a

positive school culture. A study by Quintero and colleagues (2017) found that teachers who felt that their school had a positive and supportive culture were more likely to be satisfied with their job and less likely to experience burnout. Additionally, the experiences of retired teachers can provide insights into the importance of professional development. A study by Raras and colleagues (2019) found that teachers who participated in professional development opportunities were more likely to feel confident in their teaching abilities and more likely to be

satisfied with their job. The authors suggest that ongoing professional development can help teachers stay up-to-date with the latest teaching techniques and technologies, which can improve their teaching practice and student learning outcomes. Finally, the experiences of retired

teachers can provide insights into the importance of work-life balance. A study by Bautista and colleagues (2016) found that teachers who reported having a good work-life balance were more likely to be satisfied with their job and less likely to experience burnout.

3.3.1. Positive School Culture—Positive school culture is an essential factor in ensuring the success of educational institutions. It influences the behavior, attitudes, and beliefs of both the faculty and students. A positive school culture promotes a sense of community, a climate of trust, and a shared sense of purpose among its members. Retired teachers, with their wealth of experiences, can provide educational insights on how a positive school culture can impact student learning outcomes. Leithwood et al. (2016) emphasized the importance of a positive school culture in fostering student achievement. The researchers found that schools with positive cultures had higher student achievement levels, more committed and satisfied teachers, and better overall school functioning. Gonzalez et al. (2020) explored the relationship between school culture and teacher retention rates. The researchers found that schools with positive cultures had higher teacher retention rates and were more effective in retaining experienced teachers.

Noddings (2022) emphasized the importance of caring and nurturing school cultures in promoting student well-being and academic success. The researcher argued that a culture of care and concern for students fosters positive relationships between students and teachers, promotes student engagement, and encourages students to take responsibility for their learning. According to a study by Mariano and dela Cruz (2016), positive school culture is characterized by trust, collaboration, respect, and a shared vision among stakeholders. Positive school culture is associated with higher levels of academic achievement, student engagement, and teacher retention. Ramos and Santiago (2018) explored the relationship between positive school culture and teacher motivation. The study found that teachers who perceived their school to have a positive culture reported higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation. Positive school culture was associated with supportive leadership, professional development opportunities, and a sense of community among teachers.

3.3.2. Leadership on School Culture—School culture is an important aspect of the educational system that greatly influences the teaching and learning process. Leaders, particularly school heads, play a vital role in creating a positive school culture that promotes academic excellence, collaboration, and support among the members of the school community. Bonifacio (2019) explored the perceptions of teachers and school heads on the leadership practices that promote positive school culture.

The study found that the effective leadership of school heads greatly contributes to the creation of a positive school culture that fosters a sense of belongingness and collaboration among the members of the school community. Wang and Cheng (2019) in the international setting examined the impact of distributed leadership on school culture. The study found that the distribution of leadership roles among the school community members can promote a sense of ownership and shared responsibility, leading to

the development of a positive school culture that supports the teaching and learning process. Hakanen and Siltaloppi (2021) explored the relationship between leadership and teacher well-being. The study found that supportive leadership practices, such as providing resources and recognition, can improve teachers' well-being, leading to a more positive school culture and better academic outcomes. Gurr and Drysdale (2017) explored the impact of distributed leadership, or the delegation of leadership responsibilities among different school community members, on school culture in Australia.

3.3.3. Reflection and Self-Care—Reflection and self-care are crucial aspects of a teacher's professional development and well-being. Retired teachers can offer valuable insights into the importance of these practices, as they have had years of experience dealing with the stresses and demands of the teaching profession. Through their experiences, retired teachers can provide valuable lessons on integrating reflection and self-care into a teacher's daily routine, and how these practices can lead to improved teaching performance and overall well-being. Reflection involves looking back on one's experiences and examining them critically, to improve future performance. This can help teachers identify areas where they need to grow and develop, help them appreciate their successes, and build confidence in their abilities. Self-care, on the other hand, involves taking deliberate steps to care for oneself physically and emotionally. This can include exercise, healthy eating, and taking time for hobbies and relaxation. The results of the discussions reveal that a common insight was a reflection of some concern or school issues about the school leadership, which was observed to have a positive role

They found that distributed leadership positively impacted school culture by fostering a sense of collective responsibility and ownership over the school's mission and goals. Overall, the literature suggests that leadership plays a crucial role in shaping school culture and that a positive school culture can significantly impact student outcomes. Educational insights can be drawn from the experiences of retired teachers who have witnessed firsthand the effects of different leadership styles on school culture and student success.

model for their staff, encouraging them to prioritize their own well-being and professional growth. Incorporating reflective practice and self-care into professional development can promote ongoing learning and growth among teachers, leading to continuous improvement in the school community. Abiog and Mandin (2019) explored the experiences of retired teachers in the Philippines and found that reflective practices helped them become more effective teachers. Through reflective practices, the teachers identified areas for improvement in their teaching methods and developed strategies to address these areas. Espinosa et al. (2017) found that reflective practices and self-care were essential components of teacher well-being in the Philippine context. The study highlighted the need for schools to provide opportunities for teachers to engage in these practices and support their overall well-being. In addition, a study by Pante (2018) explored the experiences of retired teachers in the Philippines and found that engaging in self-reflection helped them to cope with the challenges of the teaching profession. The study emphasized the importance of self-care practices and encouraged teachers to care for their physical and mental health to avoid burnout.

Fig. 5. Emerging themes on Educational Insights can be Drawn from the Experiences of the Retired Teachers

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the study summary was presented. From the summary of the findings, the implications and future directions were drawn.

4.1. Findings—My study aimed to understand and describe the teachers' approaches through digital narratives in Cluster 4 in enhancing learners' comprehension. To achieve the research objectives, a qualitative phenomenological method was utilized with thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, this interview approach encouraged participants to present their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored.

The preceding statements were the study's findings resulting from the merging themes generated from the participants' responses. The study's findings on the experiences of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The educational learning insights, including policy and guidelines, collaboration and sharing of resources, assessment and evaluation criteria, and professional development, have significant implications for the educational system. The implications of the studies on the experiences of retired teachers in coping with challenges in the educational setting are significant for educational management. Here are some of the implications: School leaders may foster a positive school culture prioritizing collaboration, teamwork, and mutual respect among teachers. This can lead to improved morale, job satisfaction, and, ultimately, better student outcomes. School leaders may also consider implementing strategies to support teachers' self-care and well-being, as this can help prevent burnout and pro-

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their service as public school teachers found that they were challenged by positive Esprit De Corps on teamwork and collaboration, Negative Esprit De Corps on authoritarian and micro-managed, and the impact on learning outcomes. The coping mechanisms of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers revealed that they cope through developing positive relationships with co-teachers, finding meaning in their work, and practicing self-care. Educational management insights gained from the retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers proposed the importance of building positive school culture, the significance of the impact of leadership on school culture, and reflection and self-care in order to make the teaching profession more meaningful.

mote long-term retention of quality educators. Reflection as a professional development and growth tool should also be emphasized, with opportunities for teachers to engage in ongoing self-assessment and learning. Effective leadership at all levels is crucial in promoting positive school culture and supporting teachers in their work. Leaders should work to foster trust, open communication, and collaboration among staff. Schools and educational organizations may prioritize ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers, particularly in self-care, teamwork, leadership, and positive school culture. Overall, the experiences and insights of retired teachers offer valuable lessons for educational management, with implications for how schools can create supportive, collaborative, and effective learning environments for teachers and students.

4.3. *Future Directions*—Based on the findings of the study on experiences of retired teachers' narratives and stories based on the management style of the school heads during their service as public school teachers. The future directions are as follows: The School Principal may focus on creating a positive school culture that promotes teamwork, collaboration, and self-care among teachers. They should also provide opportunities for professional development, leadership training, and mentorship programs to enhance the teachers' skills and knowledge. Additionally, they should ensure that teachers are involved in decision-making processes that affect their work environment and teaching practices. Teachers may practice self-care and reflection to manage the stresses and challenges of their work. They should also prioritize building positive relationships with colleagues and students and seek opportunities for collaboration and teamwork. Moreover, they may continuously enhance their teaching skills through professional development and leadership training. The Stakeholders, Including Parents and The Community, may support the efforts of the school principal and teachers in promoting a positive school culture that benefits students' learning outcomes. They should also advocate for policies that address the challenges teachers face in their work and contribute to building a supportive environment for the education sector. To Future Researchers, the study provides insights into retired teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms concerning school culture, leadership practices, and self-care. Future research can build on these findings by exploring other factors that affect teacher well-being and retention, such as workload, compensation, and support from school administrators and policy-makers. Additionally, studies can examine the effectiveness of various programs and initiatives to improve teacher well-being and retention in different educational contexts. In conclusion, the study provides insights and practical implications that can guide educational management practices in promoting a positive school culture, enhancing teacher well-being, and improving students' learning outcomes. These future directions can help create a conducive work environment for teachers and contribute to the overall improvement of the education system.

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